

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF SELECTED YOGIC EXERCISES ON BODY MASS INDEX OF MALE KABADDI PLAYERS

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Abstract

Yogic practices have more scientific base and make better psychological cum physiological changes in the sportspersons. In the life of sportspersons physiological condition of the athlete have much more importance. In the study effort to enlighten the positive impact of yogic exercises on body mass index of sixteen male kabaddi players of district muzaffarnagar. Lean body mass is also key factor to the performance of elite athletes. Body mass index is surrogate measure of body fatness. Scientific studies in that field are much more needed to excel or advance in indigenous games.

Keywords: *Body mass index, yoga, kabaddi, performance, indigenous, fitness, lean body mass, obesity*

INTRODUCTION

The term yoga is extracted from the Sanskrit root 'yuj' which explained as 'to join', 'to meet' or 'to add'. Yoga describes as harmony or union of oneself with that one ultimate power or god. Yogic culture is our ancient culture. It is practiced since Vedas time as yoga is described in holy books of Vedas. Yoga is a practical science and to be practiced to mastery on it. Yoga should be always done in presence of experienced trainers and yogic gurus. Yogic practices are more scientific and make better psycho cum physiological changes. Yoga enlightens the path of success, peace and healthy life. Yoga is the much needed vital fitness activity. Today in the era of science, it has found that continuous yoga activities enhance and maintain healthy life but also restrict the onset of diseases.

Body mass index is a technique among the several anthropometrical measurements which is used to measure the lean body mass of human being. Except other anthropometrical measurements body mass index is a surrogate measurement of body fatness. Body mass index is a reflection of lean tissue and fat tissue in a comparative degree. Major measurements of body mass index are height and weight to place people into normal weight, under weight, over weight and obesity. Body mass index helps to access future health issues and used as factor in health policies. Obesity is the disorder in which excess fat tissue stored in body.

Kabaddi is our indigenous sport as its origin is in India. Game of kabaddi needed quick reflexes, strength and agility. A kabaddi player should have optimum lean body mass and less fat tissues. Kabaddi is the sport majorly played in rural India. Today is need to does scientific studies and researches on our indigenous games. These studies inform players and coaches about scientific aspects of sports.

SELECTION OF SUBJECTS

Sixty male kabaddi players will be selected randomly. The age limit of subjects is (16-20). It will be checked that no one is having any kind of therapeutic treatment.

SELECTION OF VARIABLES

In the study investigator uses the body mass index formula to calculate the bmi.

The following yogic exercises that are associated to the active performance of the knee pain will be chosen for the study.

1. VIRABHADRASANA/THE WARRIOR POSE
2. TRIKONSASANA
3. UTKATASANA/CHAIR POSE
4. SETU BANDHASANA/BRIDGE POSE
5. PADAHASTASANA/ STANDING FORWARDED BEND
6. PASCHIMOTTANASANA/ SEATED FORWARD BEND
7. DANDASANA
8. VIRASANA/ HERO POSE
9. TADASANA/MOUNTAIN POSE
10. BANANASANA/BANANA POSE

Collection of data

All the subjects of the study were informed about aims and objectives of the study and requested for their cooperation. The subjects were explained about variables required for the study with necessary instructions.

Analysis and interpretation of data

Table-2.1 shows the findings of experimental group. The table shows the pre and post value of mean, pre and post value of standard deviation, pre and post value of standard error of deviation and p-value.

EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST
MEAN	24.133	22.967
SD	3.579	2.785
SED	0.653	0.509
T-RATIO	3.4231	

Table-2.1

Table 2.1 shows that there is a significant difference between pre and post value of mean and standard deviation. So the calculated value shows that there is a significant improvement in body mass index of experimental group.

Table 2.2 shows the findings of control group. The table shows the pre and post value of mean, pre and post value of standard deviation, pre and post value of standard error of deviation and p-value.

CONTROL GROUP	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST
MEAN	23.400	23.067
SD	2.908	2.406
SED	0.531	0.439
T-RATIO	0.010	

Table-2.2

Table 2.2 shows that there is no significant difference between pre and post value of mean and standard deviation. So the calculated value shows that there is no significant improvement in body mass index of control group.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of findings it can be concluded that yogic exercises improves body mass index .On the basis of our study it can also be concluded that on the basis of yogic exercise body mass index and our health status can also be improved. One can also be able to avoid health issues and risk of obesity like diseases.

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